

On Variation of Equivalent Conductance of Strong 1 : 1 Electrolytes According to Cube-root of Concentration Between 0.00001 N and 0.1 N

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In previous publications the expression for κ (Kappa) of the Debye-Hückel theory of strong electrolytes has been modified. In this paper using this modified κ (Kappa) equations have been deduced for λ , the equivalent conductance of solutions of strong electrolytes. These equations cover a wide range of concentration from 0.00002 N to 0.1 N of solutions of 1 : 1 strong electrolytes and according to them λ varies as $(C)^{1/3}$, C representing concentration in moles per liter. The equations have been subjected to test using the data available in the literature on HCl, KCl, NaCl, KNO₃, and AgNO₃, and have been found satisfactory.

It has been found that A, the "effective diameter", of the ions occurring in the equations, has different values in the different zones of concentration of the electrolytes used. The value of A of each of the chlorides above 0.001 N is much smaller than that below it. In the case of each of the nitrates, A has the highest value below 0.0008 N and the lowest value above 0.005 N. Within the range 0.005 N to 0.0008 N, it has an intermediate value. Since the change in A indicates change in hydration of the ions, the effect of its change on the size and mobility of the ions has been considered.

In earlier publications¹⁻³, the necessity of modifying the expression for κ (Kappa) of the Debye-Hückel theory^{4,5} of strong electrolytes has been discussed and the expression for κ_m , the modified Kappa, which has been deduced for 1 : 1 strong electrolytes may be written as follows :

$$\kappa_m = \left[\frac{4\pi e^3 2n f_0}{DkT f} \right]^{1/2} \dots (1)$$

where π , e , D , k , T have their usual significance, $2n$ represents the sum of n_+ and n_- ions per cc and f_0 and f denote the mean activity coefficient of the ions in the bulk of the solution and in the ion atmosphere of the central ion, respectively.

Applying Donnan's theory⁶ of membrane equilibrium, f_0/f in equation (1) can be put equal to n^1/n and assuming uniform distribution of ions, $2n$ can be put equal to $\left(\frac{1}{L}\right)^3$ where L is the average distance between two neighbouring ions. Now putting $L=2\pi ax$, introducing these changes in equation (1) and simplifying, it may be written as follows :

$$\kappa_m = (2n)^{1/2} \left[\frac{2e^3}{DkT a} \right]^{1/2} \left[\frac{n^1/n}{x} \right]^{1/2} \dots (2)$$

where n^1 and n represent respectively the number of ions per unit volume in the ion atmosphere and bulk of the solution, $n^1 > n$, a is the minimum distance of approach between two oppositely charged ions and x , a dimensionless variable.

It may be mentioned that as n increases both n^1/n and x decrease. It has, therefore, been assumed that over a certain range of values of n ,

$\left[\frac{n^1/n}{x} \right]$ may remain constant. It then follows that

within that range of values of n , κ_m will vary as $(2n)^{1/2}$ since all the other terms in equation (2) are constants. Next, putting $n=NC/1000$ and

$\left[\frac{n^1/n}{x} \right] = \theta$, a constant and $a/\theta = A$, in equation (2)

it may be expressed as follows :

$$\kappa_m = \frac{B}{\sqrt{A}} (C)^{1/2} \dots (3)$$

where B contains all the other constant terms[†] and for a 1 : 1 electrolyte at 25° it is equal to 0.4024×10^8 , A being expressed in Angström unit. Henceforth A will be referred to as the effective ionic diameter. It may be mentioned that in previous publications^{1,2} reasons have been put forward for treating θ to be close to unity and we shall follow the same treatment here also.

Equation for equivalent conductance :

The Debye-Hückel-Onsager⁷ equation for equivalent conductance, which is of the same form as the Kohlrausch's⁸ square root law may be written

$$\dagger B = (2e^3/DkT)^{1/2} (2N/1000)^{1/2} (10^{-4})$$

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as follows :

$$\lambda = \lambda_0 - (A_1 \lambda_0 + B_2) \kappa \quad \dots (4)$$

$$= \lambda_0 - (A_1 \lambda_0 + B_2) B_0 (C)^{1/2} \quad \dots (4a)$$

$$= \lambda_0 - S(C)^{1/2} \quad \dots (LL)$$

where λ_0 is the limiting equivalent conductance, $\kappa = B_0(C)^{1/2}$ and A_1 , B_2 and B_0 are constants which can be calculated from theory. In equation (LL), $S = (A_1 \lambda_0 + B_2) B_0$.

Replacing the Debye-Hückel κ by the modified κ_m , we may express the modified equation for equivalent conductance as follows :

$$\lambda = \lambda_g - (A_1 \lambda_0 + B_2) \kappa_m \quad \dots (5)$$

$$= \lambda_g - (A_1 \lambda_0 + B_2) \frac{B}{\sqrt{A}} (C)^{1/2} \quad \dots (5a)$$

$$= \lambda_g - \frac{m}{\sqrt{A}} (C)^{1/2} \quad \dots (6)$$

In equations (5) to (6) λ_g is a characteristic constant which represents the equivalent conductance at infinite dilution and in equation (6), $m = (A_1 \lambda_0 + B_2) B$. At 25° for a 1:1 electrolyte $A_1 = 0.6989 \times 10^{-6}$, $B_2 = 184.3 \times 10^{-6}$ and $B = 0.4024 \times 10^6$.

It has been found that although λ varies with $(C)^{1/2}$ as represented in equation (6) yet there is, at a sufficiently low concentration, a narrow transition zone of concentration for each electrolyte below which the value of A is much larger and that of λ_g smaller than that above it. Since change in the value of A is attributed to change in hydration of the ions^{8,9}, the aforesaid observation leads to the conclusion that ionic hydration in different regions of concentration has got different values. In the case of the nitrates of Ag and K three such regions have been detected. Equation (6) has, therefore, been represented by (6a), (6b) and (6c) with different values of A and λ_g to indicate the changes in hydration of the ions.

It may be mentioned that for a given electrolyte, λ_g in equation (6a) in the concentration range below 0.0009 N can be related to λ_0 by the following equation :

$$\lambda_0 = \lambda_g - \frac{m}{\sqrt{A}} (C_0)^{1/2} \quad \dots (7)$$

$$= \lambda_g - 0.68 \text{ (approximately)} \quad \dots (7a)$$

In equation (7), C_0 is the characteristic concentration at which λ_0 is reached.

In the following section the equations (6a)-(6c) and (7a) have been subjected to test, selecting such electrolytes the data of which are available in the literature covering the concentration range 0.00001 N to 0.1 N.

Processing of data and verification of the equations :

The data recorded in the Tables have been collected from Shedlovsky's¹⁰ paper. In column 1

under the head miscellaneous are mentioned the electrolyte and the equation used and the values of the constants in the equation, C represents concentration in moles per liter. In Table 2, Obs. λ and Calcd. λ denote observed and calculated values of equivalent conductance.

In Table 3 are recorded the values of λ_g of equation (6a) and λ_0 of equation (LL). In column

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF EQUIVALENT CONDUCTANCE WITH CONCENTRATION AT 25°

Miscellaneous	O × 10 ⁴	Observed λ	λ Calcd. using		
			Eqn. (LL)	Eqn. (6a)	Eqn. (6b)
HCl	0.2841	425.01	425.31	425.27	
Eqn. LL	0.8118	424.75	424.79	424.60	
$\lambda_0 = 426.16$	1.774	423.82	424.05	423.91	
$S = 158.7$	3.186	423.43	423.33	423.27	
Eqn. (6a)	3.423	423.22	423.21	423.18	
$\lambda_g = 426.89$	5.915	422.42	422.30	422.44	422.53
$m/(A)^{1/2} = 53.0$	10.00	421.24	421.14	421.59	421.21
$(A) = 19.4 \text{ \AA}$	20.00	419.27	419.11		419.08
	50.00	415.68	414.94		415.40
Eqn. (6b)					
$\lambda_g = 429.41$	100.00	411.88			411.76
$m/(A)^{1/2} = 82.0$	200.00	407.12			407.16
$(A) = 5.59 \text{ \AA}$	1000.0	391.20			391.35
KCl	0.3258	149.33	149.32	149.44	
Eqn. LL	1.045	148.91	148.89	148.89	
$\lambda_0 = 149.86$	3.328	148.19	148.12	148.10	
$S = 95.1$	4.695	147.89	147.67	147.79	
Eqn. (6a)	8.420	147.23	147.10	147.19	
$\lambda_g = 150.59$	10.00	146.93	146.85	146.99	146.95
$m/(A)^{1/2} = 36.0$	20.00	145.79	145.61		145.66
$(A) = 10.1 \text{ \AA}$	50.00	143.55	143.14		143.42
Eqn. (6b)	100.00	141.32			141.22
$\lambda_g = 151.84$	200.00	138.34			138.43
$m/(A)^{1/2} = 49.7$	1000.0	128.96			128.87
$(A) = 5.48 \text{ \AA}$					
NaCl	0.5944	125.79	125.76	125.81	
Eqn. LL	1.128	125.57	125.50	125.51	
$\lambda_0 = 126.45$	1.899	125.09	125.22	125.20	
$S = 89.78$	4.268	124.58	124.60	124.61	
	6.790	124.21	124.11	124.20	
Eqn. (6a)	6.920	124.21	124.09	124.18	
$\lambda_g = 127.10$	10.00	123.72	123.61	123.80	123.75
$m/(A)^{1/2} = 38.0$	20.00	122.67	122.44	122.94	122.54
$(A) = 10.0 \text{ \AA}$	50.00	120.58	120.12		120.44
Eqn. (6b)	100.00	118.43			118.38
$\lambda_g = 128.41$	200.0	115.76			115.76
$m/(A)^{1/2} = 46.6$	1000.0	106.74			106.78
$(A) = 5.52 \text{ \AA}$					
KNO ₃	0.6782	144.17	144.17	144.15	
Eqn. LL	1.761	143.62	143.71	143.61	
$\lambda_0 = 144.96$	3.889	142.98	143.11	143.00	
$S = 93.99$	5.865	142.61	142.68	142.62	
Eqn. (6a)	8.685	141.97	142.19	142.20	142.14
$\lambda_g = 145.61$	10.00	141.80	142.09		141.90
$m/(A)^{1/2} = 35.7$	16.47	140.91			140.96
$(A) = 10.4 \text{ \AA}$	20.00	140.54			140.55
Eqn. (6b)	24.32	140.17			140.22
$\lambda_g = 147.10$	36.72	139.08			139.08
$m/(A)^{1/2} = 52.0$					
$(A) = 4.88 \text{ \AA}$					

(Table 1 Contd.)

AgNO ₃	0.2758	132.91	132.88	132.94	
Eqn. LL	0.7245	132.64	132.58	132.62	
	1.071	132.48	132.48	132.43	
$\lambda_g = 133.36$	3.539	131.58	131.64	131.66	
$S = 91.3$	4.671	131.46	131.39	131.46	
Eqn. (6a)	5.000	131.32	131.32	131.38	131.45
$\lambda_g = 134.00$	7.538	130.82	130.85	131.00	130.89
$m/(A)^{1/2} = 33.0$	10.00	130.47	130.35		130.46
$(A) = 11.4 \text{ \AA}$	14.53	129.86	129.88		129.83
Eqn. (6b)	29.05	128.44	128.44		128.41
$\lambda_g = 135.25$	50.00	127.16	126.90		127.06
$m/(A)^{1/2} = 47.9$					
$(A) = 5.48 \text{ \AA}$					

4 of the table, the values of λ_0 calculated by using equation (7a) are recorded.

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF λ WITH C AT 25°

Miscellaneous	C	0.005	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
KNO ₃	Obs. λ	138.44	135.78	132.37	126.27	120.36
Eqn. (6c)						
$\lambda_g = 149.31$						
$m/(A)^{1/2} = 62.4$	Calcd. λ	138.64	135.87	132.37	126.32	120.35
$(A) = 3.39 \text{ \AA}$						
AgNO ₃	C	0.005	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
Eqn. (6c)	Obs. λ	127.16	124.72	121.37	115.20	109.10
$\lambda_g = 138.11$						
$m/(A)^{1/2} = 62.2$	Calcd. λ	127.47	124.72	121.32	115.20	109.24
$(A) = 3.20 \text{ \AA}$						

TABLE 3— λ_0 CALCULATED BY USING EQUATION (7a)

Electrolyte	λ_g	Obs. λ_0	Calcd. λ_0 Eqn. (7a)
HCl	426.89	426.16	426.21
KCl	150.59	149.86	149.91
NaCl	127.10	126.45	126.42
KNO ₃	145.61	144.95	144.93
AgNO ₃	134.00	133.36	133.32

Discussion

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table 1 that for each of the chlorides the values of λ calculated by using the equations (6a) and (6b) agree well with those observed over the concentration range 0.00001 N to 0.1 N; equation (6a) holding good below 0.001 N and equation (6b) above it. In the case of the nitrates, equation (6b) holds good upto about 0.005 N and above that equation (6c) holds good. It may be mentioned that variation of λ in accordance with the cube root of concentration was first predicted by Ghosh¹¹ from theoretical considerations.

It is to be noted that the value of A (indicating hydration⁹) in equation (6a) is much greater than that in equation (6b) and that the increase occurs within a narrow zone of concentration usually between 0.0007 N and 0.0009 N. Since below this

zone the value of A (indicating hydration) is almost twice as large as that above it, it may be inferred that both the ions, cation and anion of the electrolyte used, become more heavily hydrated at high dilution (below 0.001 M).

In the low concentration region below 0.001 N, the values of λ of each of the electrolytes calculated by using equation (LL) and equation (6a) agree well with those observed. Hence, both the equations hold good in this region, but equation (LL) has the advantage that one of its constants, S, can be calculated from theory and that its validity extends over a slightly wider range than that of (6a). It may also be mentioned that after the limiting concentration at which f_0/f in κ_m becomes unity is reached, equation (6a) should cease to hold good, but equation (LL) should still remain valid theoretically. It is quite likely, however, that this limiting concentration is of the same order as C₀ in equation (7).

An examination of the data of the nitrates in the Tables 1 and 2 indicates that the change in the value of A occurs not only below 0.0009 N but also above 0.005 N. It also appears from the values of A that in the concentration region below 0.0009 N the nitrates are as heavily hydrated as the chlorides, but in the concentration region above 0.005 N they are very little hydrated. The Pauling radius of the nitrate ion cannot be less than that of the chloride ion. Assuming it to be the same as that of the Cl⁻ ion, the sum of the crystallographic radius of the ions of KNO₃ and AgNO₃ should be 3.14 Å and 3.07 Å, respectively and the corresponding observed values of A are 3.39 Å and 3.20 Å. Thus at relatively high concentrations, i.e. above 0.005 N, the ions of the nitrates are almost without hydration and this observation is in agreement with the widely accepted view¹² that the nitrate ion is a "strong structure breaker". It is to be noted, however, that the aforesaid widely accepted view on the "structure breaking" property of the nitrate ion is valid at relatively high concentration only (i.e. above 0.005 N).

The data recorded in Tables 1 and 2 also show that as concentration decreases, hydration of the ions, as indicated by A, increases at different levels of concentration and λ_g decreases, as it should do, since the size of the ions increases owing to increase in hydration. In the concentration region below 0.0009 N, λ_g of equation (6a) of a given electrolyte has got the lowest value and it is fairly close to λ_0 of equation (LL) of the same electrolyte and the two can be correlated by equation (7). It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table 3 that the agreement between the observed and calculated value of λ_0 of any one of the electrolytes mentioned is within ± 0.035 per cent.

In conclusion, it may be stated that the equations (6a)-(6c) account not only for the variation of λ according to cube root of concentration over a wide range, 0.00001 N to 0.1 N, but also give useful

information on the hydration of ions of electrolytes at different levels of concentration of the solutions.

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